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D11.2 Application toolkit

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18	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	Canada
19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

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Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
LIST OF FIGURES	6
ABBREVIATIONS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1 INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 THE VITALISE PROJECT	9
1.2 DESCRIPTION OF WP11	9
1.3 TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS	9
1.4 PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT	10
2 THE VITALISE APPLICATION TOOLKIT	11
2.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE OPEN CALLS	11
2.2 INSTRUCTIONS TO APPLY TO TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS	12
2.2.1 <i>Explore the infrastructure</i>	13
2.2.2 <i>Explore JRAs</i>	15
2.2.3 <i>Compare Infrastructures</i>	15
2.2.4 <i>Application Manual</i>	16
2.2.5 <i>FAQs</i>	17
2.2.6 <i>Application template</i>	18
2.2.7 <i>Application submission through the Toolkit</i>	18
2.2.8 <i>Contacts for TA</i>	19
2.2.9 <i>Newsletter Subscription Form</i>	19
3 THE TOOLKIT	20
3.1.1 <i>Page 1 – Administrative Form</i>	20
3.1.2 <i>Page 2 – Transnational access to the infrastructure</i>	21
3.1.3 <i>Page 3 – Project Description</i>	23
3.1.4 <i>Backend of the Online Toolkit</i>	24
4 CONCLUSIONS	25
5 APPENDICES	26
5.1 APPENDIX I	26

List of Figures

Figure 1. The application toolkit in the frame of the 3rd cut-off of the 3rd open call	11
Figure 2. Timeline of the 3rd open call for transnational access.	12
Figure 3. The application toolkit in the frame of the 2nd open call for transnational access.....	12
Figure 4. Step 1 of the application toolkit: explore the infrastructures	13
Figure 5. Table listing all the research infrastructures open for transnational access	14
Figure 6. Infographics regarding living labs capacity in the frame of the 1st cut-off of the 3rd open call.	14
Figure 7. Step 2 of the application toolkit: explore the joint research activities (jras).	15
Figure 8. Step 3 of the application toolkit: compare the infrastructures	16
Figure 9. Living lab service comparison	16
Figure 10. Step 4 of the application toolkit: read the application manual	17
Figure 11. Step 5 of the application toolkit: advise faqs section in case there are any questions.	17
Figure 12. Step 6 of the application toolkit. Download the application template	18
Figure 13. Step 7 of the application toolkit: submit your application through the toolkit	18
Figure 14. Step 8 of the application toolkit: still need help?	19
Figure 15. Subscription form to the vitalise newsletters	19
Figure 16. Administrative details (affiliation)	20
Figure 17. Administrative details (applicant).....	21
Figure 18. Transnational access to the infrastructure	21
Figure 19. Select the services provided from the infrastructure	22
Figure 20. Access to infrastructure	23
Figure 21. Project description	23
Figure 22. Backend of the application form - overview	24
Figure 23. Backend of the application form - entries.....	24

Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
LL	Living Lab
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
TA	Transnational Access
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document describes in detail the Application Toolkit, an online resource available on the VITALISE Website specifically developed to enable external researchers to apply to Transnational Access and to guide them throughout the application procedure.

The Application Toolkit is structured in 3 main sections:

- Introduction to the Open Call for Transnational Access
- Instruction to Apply to Transnational Access (How Can I Apply?): the section guides the applicant throughout the application procedure, also providing useful materials to draft the application.
- Online Toolki. It consists of an application form that applicants must fill in in order to submit their application and research proposal. This last section is also enriched with a highlight on the technical development of the Online Toolkit, as well as a description of its backend.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g. healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in-person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Description of WP11

The objectives of WP11 are

- To prepare the required application templates, time plan, “how to” and FAQ for the external applicants
- To implement the open calls for Transnational Access
- To define the evaluation criteria and the evaluation procedure for the external applications for TA/VA
- To evaluate the external applications and select the researchers for the TA and VA

In order to reach these objectives, WP11 was structured in 3 different tasks:

T11.1 Design of Evaluation Procedure aimed at defining the evaluation criteria and the evaluation procedure to be applied in the 3 Open Calls for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures to select research proposals.

T11.2 Call for proposals and evaluation. This task implements the 3 Open Calls for Transnational Access.

T11.3 Application Toolkit. This task developed the application toolkit necessary for the Open Calls, composed by application templates, time plan, “how to” and FAQ (Frequently Asked Questions) to support the effective realisation of the open calls.

1.3 Transnational Access

One of the main objectives of the VITALISE project is to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain by enabling in-person Transnational Access to all the Research Infrastructures involved in the project and to encourage Virtual Access to the VITALISE database.

Through the Open Calls for Transnational Access researchers from multiple disciplines can access one of the 17 Living Lab Research Infrastructures to conduct their own research study. TA can be fully in-person, partially remote (i.e., a period in-person and a period of remote access to the infrastructure’s facilities) or fully remote, based on the research needs of each project. During the in-person TA the researchers will benefit of a financial support for travel subsistence and daily allowance, while there will be no refund during the remote period.

1.4 Purpose of this Document

The objective of this document is to provide a detailed description of the Application Toolkit, an online resource available on the VITALISE website and aimed at providing external researchers willing to apply to TA first-hand information on the Living Labs and their services and on the application procedure, timing and general rules to apply to the Open Calls.

2 The VITALISE Application Toolkit

The VITALISE Application Toolkit is an online resource developed in the frame of the Open Calls for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures that provided external researchers with all the necessary information and procedure to submit complete, correct and standardized applications to Transnational Access throughout the 3 Open Calls. The application toolkit has been enriched with useful online resources, which have been specifically developed to guide applicants to the identification of the most suitable research infrastructure to deploy their research project.

The application toolkit has been structured in 3 main sections:

- Introduction to the (running) Open Call. This section aims to provide first-hand information on TA, deadlines and timing of the evaluation procedures. The section has been regularly updated throughout all the 3 Open Calls.
- Instruction to Apply to Transnational Access (How Can I Apply?). This section guides the applicant through the application procedure, providing them complete information, templates and instructions to submit a successful and complete application. The application procedure is presented as a flow of activities and is enriched with additional information and inputs to allow the applicant to compare infrastructures, find answers to questions, and contact the Living Labs.
- Online Toolkit: this is the application form that applicants must fill in in order to submit their application and research proposal.

The application toolkit is available at the following link: <https://vitalise-project.eu/transnational-access-to-research-infrastructures/>.

2.1 Introduction to the Open Calls

The section introduces the reader to the ongoing Open Call. The deadline to submit the application is clearly stated in the subtitle and identifiable through graphical elements and text formatting.

Below the titles, a short paragraph introduces Transnational Access, its objectives and the general services and benefits provided by the VITALISE Consortium through the Open Calls.

The screenshot shows the VITALISE website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: About, Access to Infrastructures, Harmonisation, Capacity Building & Training, ICT Tools, Outputs, Press, and Contact. A search bar is located on the right. Below the navigation, a blue banner reads "VITALISE-PROJECT / TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS TO RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES". The main content area features the title "3rd Open Call | Transnational Access to the Research Infrastructures of VITALISE Project". Below the title, there is a red call to action: "The 3rd Open Call for Transnational Access to the Living Labs of VITALISE Project is now open and we are looking forward to receiving your applications." A red diamond icon precedes the text: "3rd Cut-off Deadline extended: July 16th, 2023". Below this, it says "Keep scrolling to find out how you can apply!". A paragraph follows: "Through the Transnational Access (TA) Programme, VITALISE project opens up 17 Living Lab Research Infrastructures located in 7 different countries to external researchers from multiple disciplines, so that they conduct their research studies for free. The applicants for Transnational Access may choose to work on their own projects or on one of the main research areas of the project, i.e., (i) Rehabilitation, (ii) Transitional care and (iii) Everyday living environments (see Joint Research Activities). Transnational Access can be (i) fully in-person, (ii) partially remote (i.e., in-person access for a specific time period combined with". To the right, there is a "Transnational Access Factsheet" and "VITALISE Info Day recordings".

Figure 1. The Application toolkit in the frame of the 3rd cut-off of the 3rd Open Call

In order to promote the submission of high-quality project proposals, VITALISE consortium leverages on standardized templates to be used by the applicants. A first recall to the official templates to be applied in the application process is already provided at this stage. The link to download the official application template is already available in this first section.

It follows a timeline of the running Open Call, that provides information on the submission windows, on the notification of the results and on the expected TA period (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Timeline of the 3rd Open Call for Transnational Access.

This first section has been regularly implemented and updated throughout the 3 Open Calls: submission deadlines, Open Call deadline and links to the Application template have been regularly updated. Below are provided the screenshots of the page during the second and the first Open Calls (Figure 3 and 4).

Figure 3. The Application Toolkit in the frame of the 2nd Open Call for Transnational Access

2.2 Instructions to Apply to Transnational Access

This section, introduced by the question “How can I apply?”, describes in detail the steps that an applicant should follow to collect all the necessary information and templates in order to submit a successful application. The section is divided into 9 steps:

1. Explore the infrastructures
2. Explore JRAs
3. Compare Infrastructures

4. Application Manual
5. FAQs
6. Application template
7. Application submission through the Toolkit
8. Contacts for TA
9. Newsletter subscription

Following, we provide a brief description of each section.

2.2.1 Explore the infrastructure

The paragraph provides the applicants with useful resources and information to explore and compare the research infrastructures open for VITALISE Transnational Access. Providing applicants with complete and detailed information is fundamental in order to enable them to choose the right infrastructure to conduct their study.

Figure 4. Step 1 of the application toolkit: Explore the Infrastructures

A table listing all the Research Infrastructures is here provided (Figure 5): each infrastructure has a related link to a dedicated webpage that describes in detail the Living Lab. Further details on this are provided in D11.1, Paragraph 4.3.2. Living Lab Research Infrastructure Description.

No.	Partner	Infrastructure
1	LICALAB	LiCalab Older Adults Homes
2	LICALAB	MOBILAB & Care – Motion lab
3	LICALAB	Thomas More Experience lab
4	AUTH	AUTH Living Environment simulation
5	AUTH	AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab
6	AUTH	AUTH Centrifuge Rehabilitation Living Lab
7	AIT	AIT Technology Experience Lab
8	TREBAG	Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab
9	GAIA	GAIA and Smart Spaces
10	GAIA	GAIA Ozean Living Lab
11	INTRAS	INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab
12	INTRAS	INTRAS VR/AR Environment and Snoezelen Room
13	INTRAS	INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living
14	McGill	McGill-UDEM-CRIR Living Lab
15	UPM	LifeSpace by UPM
16	LAUREA	Laurea Simulated Hospital
17	LAUREA	Laurea Activity Living Lab

Figure 5. Table listing all the Research Infrastructures open for Transnational Access

As the Open Calls unfolded, some Living Labs reached their full capacity to host external researchers. In order to encourage applications to Living Labs that still had availability, we decided to inform potential applicants about each partner’s capacity status concerning TA hosting. Therefore, in the frame of the 1st Cut-off of the 3rd Open Call, this section was integrated with a dedicated infographic to display each partner’s remaining capacity to host visiting researchers (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Infographics regarding Living Labs Capacity in the frame of the 1st cut-off of the 3rd Open Call.

2.2.2 Explore JRAs

Researchers are hereby encouraged to learn more about VITALISE Joint Research Activities: through a dedicated link, they are redirected to a dedicated page that describes the 3 main domains of JRA: Rehabilitation, Transnational care and Everyday living environments. External researchers may explore the ongoing researches and choose whether to present an application to jointly conduct research studies with the VITALISE consortium partners or submit their own/personal research project.

Figure 7. Step 2 of the application toolkit: Explore the Joint Research Activities (JRAs).

2.2.3 Compare Infrastructures

Applicants are encouraged to further deepen the knowledge of the research infrastructures and of the services that each one of them is offering. The application toolkit provides in this step the access to different resources to perform an effective and successful comparison between the infrastructures. We hereby provide a list of the resources and their short description:

- Contact the Living Labs. The link provides access to an online form where potential applicants can directly contact the Living Labs.
- Compare the services offered at each infrastructure. The link redirects to the Living Lab Comparison Table, that displays all the available services offered by each Living Lab involved in the VITALISE project (Figure 9).
- Compare which Living Labs have offerings according to your field of expertise. The link redirects to an online document that describes use cases according specific field of expertise: each use case is matched with Living Lab Research Infrastructures that can support the described use case (Annex I).

Figure 8. Step 3 of the Application Toolkit: Compare the Infrastructures

vitalise-project.eu/living-labs-services-comparison/

VITALISE-PROJECT / LIVING LABS SERVICES COMPARISON

X=offering, PTO=Planning to offer
Find the description of the services here.

	Living Labs of VITALISE Project								
Services	Thess-AHALL Active and Healthy Ageing Living Labs (Thessaloniki, Greece)	LiCalab – Living and Care lab (Geel & Turnhout, Belgium)	MINDLab by INTRAS Foundation (Valladolid, Spain)	Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab (Nagykovácsi, Hungary)	GAIA Living Labs (Bilbao, Spain)	AIT Health Experience Lab (Vienna, Austria)	LifeSpace by UPM (Madrid, Spain)	McGill-UDEM-CRIR Living Lab (Montreal, Canada)	Laurea Living Labs (Helsinki-Uusimaa region, Finland)
Networking and capacity building									
Capacity building	X	X	X	X	PTO		X		X
Equipment and facility rental service			PTO	X					
Expert opinion, and advisory services	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Grant writing and funding application support service	PTO			X	X				X
Temporary research									

Figure 9. Living Lab Service Comparison

2.2.4 Application Manual

The “VITALISE Project’s Application Manual to the Open Calls for Transnational Access to Research Infrastructures and for Virtual Access to the VITALISE database” is the main official resource which provides applicants a complete and detailed guidance to the application process, procedures and terms and conditions. This step provides the link to download the application manual. It also encourages applicants to read it carefully before submitting the application. Further details on the Application Manual are available in D11.1, paragraph 3. *Application Manual for TA and VA*. The application Manual is also provided as Annex to D11.1.

Figure 10. Step 4 of the Application Toolkit: Read the Application Manual

2.2.5 FAQs

FAQs are available in a dedicated page, accessible through a dedicated link. Further details on FAQs are available in D11.1, paragraph 4.3.6 *FAQs and direct support page*. In case the topic is not addressed in the FAQs, applicants can find here a dedicated e-mail address where to forward specific inquiries and receive support.

Figure 11. Step 5 of the Application Toolkit: Advise FAQs section in case there are any questions.

2.2.6 Application template

All the research proposals have to be developed according to the Application Template provided by the VITALISE Consortium. At this stage, applicants can download the .doc version of the application template. Further details on the Application Template are provided in D11.1, paragraph 4.1 *Application Template*. The application Template is also provided as Annex to D11.1.

Figure 12. Step 6 of the Application Toolkit. Download the application template

2.2.7 Application submission through the Toolkit

A link to the Toolkit to submit applications is hereby provided. The link redirects to a dedicated page provided of a digital application form, where applicants can fill in all their general data, choose the infrastructure and upload the application. Further description of the Toolkit is provided in chapter 3.

Figure 13. Step 7 of the Application Toolkit: Submit your application through the Toolkit

2.2.8 Contacts for TA

The applicants still in need of support or clarifications to submit their application can contact the general inquiry email address (info@vitalise.eu). In case they have specific requests concerning a specific Living Lab they can also find the direct contact with the RILs. A complete list of the RILs and their email contacts is also provided through a dedicated page.

Figure 14. Step 8 of the Application Toolkit: Still need help?

2.2.9 Newsletter Subscription Form

Finally, the applicants can choose to subscribe to VITALISE Newsletter to be constantly updated on the Open Calls and/or any other of the VITALISE Project.

A screenshot of a newsletter subscription form. At the top, it says "Subscribe below to be the first one to get informed when we launch an Open Call!". Below this is a "Subscribe" section with a "Subscribe" button. The form includes three input fields: "Email Address *" (with a note "* indicates required"), "First Name", and "Last Name". Underneath these is an "Opt-In Groups" section with three checkboxes: "VITALISE Project Newsletter" (checked), "VITALISE Harmonization Body" (unchecked), and "VITALISE Open Calls" (checked).

Figure 15. Subscription form to the VITALISE Newsletters

3 The Toolkit

The VITALISE Online Toolkit is an application form that allows users to submit their proposals for the VITALISE open calls. The toolkit is accessible through the following url: [vitalise-project.eu/openhttps://vitalise-project.eu/open-calls/calls/](https://vitalise-project.eu/open-calls/calls/).

For the technical realization of the Application Toolkit, a website plugin compatible with WordPress platform was customized by VILABS to cover the needs of VITALISE Open Calls. The plugin is named **WPForms**: through it, website contact forms can be built without the need of writing html code. The Application Toolkit was created by customizing the features and templates provided by WPForms. All forms created for the Application Toolkit were completely responsive, mobile-friendly and compatible with all modern web browsers. It should be noted that no third party was able to access the information collected.

Ensuring a homogeneous and standardized collection of the data related to the project proposals and to the research team is paramount to understand whether the project proposals are in line with objectives and purposes of the VITALISE Project, and whether the Research Infrastructure are in the conditions to provide the required support. Moreover, the Toolkit has established a common standard in the collection of the personal data of the researchers and of the project proposal structure within the frame of each Open Call and related cut-off. This significantly simplified the application procedure for applicants and ensured a quick evaluation procedure within each Open Call.

3.1.1 Page 1 – Administrative Form

In the first page of the application toolkit (Figure 16, Figure 17) the user is requested to fill the following administrative information:

- Details of applicant(s) affiliation: Name, Address, Country, Domain, website
- Number of applicants (select up to 5), and for every applicant:
 - Name, gender, nationality, email, telephone number, position in the affiliated institution.

Figure 16. Administrative Details (Affiliation)

Private | Other | vitalise-project.eu/open-calls/

Nagykovács Wellbeing Living Lab - Trebag
Laurea Activity Living Lab
AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

Website *

How many applicants in total (up to 5)?

No of applicants: 1

First Applicant (User Group Leader/Reference person)

Name *

First Last

Gender

Nationality *

Email *

Email Confirm Email

Telephone number *

Position held in the affiliated institute *

Next

Figure 17. Administrative Details (Applicant).

3.1.2 Page 2 – Transnational access to the infrastructure

After filling in the above-mentioned information, the user clicks on the Next button. In the next page, the user is requested to select up to three Infrastructures in order of preference (Figure 18).

Private | vitalise-project.eu/open-calls/

VITALISE | About | Infrastructure | Publications | Press | Harmonisation | Access to Infrastructures | Contact | Search

VITALISE-PROJECT / OPEN-CALLS

1 Administrative form | 2 Transnational access to the infrastructure | 3 Project description

Select up to 3 infrastructures in order of preference

Infrastructure 1: *

select an infrastructure (first option mandatory)

Infrastructure 2:

select an infrastructure

Infrastructure 3:

select an infrastructure

Would you consider reallocation to similar Infrastructures by VITALISE recommendation? *

Yes

No

How long do you need to access the infrastructure approximately? (Suggested 30 continuous days) *

Preferable starting period? (From the beginning of September 2022 to the end of November 2022) *

Beginning of September 2022

Previous Next

VITALISE infrastructures

Rehabilitation

- AUTH Centrifuge Rehabilitation Living Lab
- Thomas More MOTION lab - Mobilab
- GAIA and Ocean Living Lab for Rehabilitation
- INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab

Transitions in care

- AUTH Health Care Transitions Living Lab
- INTRAS VR/AR and Snoezelen Room
- Thomas More Experience Lab
- UPM-LifeSTech- The Smart House Living Lab
- Laurea Simulated Hospital
- McGill - CRIR rehabilitation Living Lab

Smart environments

- AUTH Living environment simulation
- GAIA Smart Spaces
- INTRAS MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living
- LICslab Older Adults' Homes
- Nagykovács Wellbeing Living Lab - Trebag
- Laurea Activity Living Lab
- AIT Technology Experience Laboratory

Figure 18. Transnational Access to the Infrastructure

D11.2 Application Toolkit

For every infrastructure, the following information is mandatory:

- Previous user of the infrastructure? (Yes, No)
- Do you have access to equivalent installations in your country of affiliation? (Yes, No)

Users are also requested to select the services of the infrastructure that they might want to use (services differ for each infrastructure).

- Do you need any specific service provided from the infrastructure to carry out your project? (If yes, please select ONLY the services that you actually need to execute your research project, as described in your project description)

1 Administrative form 2 Transnational access to the infrastructure 3 Project description

Select up to 3 infrastructures in order of preference

Infrastructure 1: *

AUTH Living environment simulation (Thessaloniki, Greece) ▾

Previous user of the infrastructure? *

Yes

No

Do you have access to equivalent installations in your country of affiliation? *

Yes

No

Do you need any specific service provided from the infrastructure to carry out your project? (If yes, please select ONLY the services that you actually need to execute your research project, as described in your project description)

[Click here to view more info about the services](#)

- Capacity building (Networking and capacity building)
- Expert opinion, and advisory services (Networking and capacity building)
- Innovation network orchestration (Networking and capacity building)
- Panel management (Networking and capacity building)
- Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping (Networking and capacity building)
- Intake and matching (Project planning and management)
- Expert opinion, and advisory services (Project planning and management)
- Living lab project planning and management (Project planning and management)
- Access to data (Market and competitor intelligence services)
- Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking (Market and competitor intelligence services)
- Expert opinion, and advisory services (Market and competitor intelligence services)
- Co-creation session (co-creation)
- Expert opinion, and advisory services (co-creation)
- Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping (co-creation)
- Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping (Market and competitor intelligence services)
- Clinical trials (Testing and validation)
- Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study (Testing and validation)
- Expert opinion, and advisory services (Testing and validation)
- Idea selection and testing (Testing and validation)
- Impact assessment and validation test (Testing and validation)
- Large-scale real-life testing and piloting (Testing and validation)
- Prototyping test (Testing and validation)
- Simulation test (Testing and validation)
- Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation (Testing and validation)
- Usability testing (Testing and validation)

Infrastructure 2:

select an infrastructure ▾

Infrastructure 3:

select an infrastructure ▾

Figure 19. Select the services provided from the infrastructure

Finally, in this page the user is requested to fill in the following information (Figure 20):

- Would you consider reallocation to similar Infrastructures by VITALISE recommendation?
- How long do you need to access the infrastructure approximately? (Suggested 30 continuous days)
- Preferable starting period?

Figure 20. Access to infrastructure

3.1.3 Page 3 – Project Description

In the last page of the application form, the user is requested to fill in the following information regarding the submitting research project:

- Title
- Acronym
- Abstract

This is also the place where the user is requested to upload the “Project description”.

Before submitting the application, the user is requested to Agree with the VITALISE Privacy Policy.

Figure 21. Project Description

3.1.4 Backend of the Online Toolkit

Following the technical realization of the toolkit for the VITALISE Open Calls, website administrators (VILABS) have access to all applications and their corresponding data at a backend level through the Wordpress platform. In this manner, the new registrations are examined, encompassing the applicants' details, the application date, as well as all information regarding potential transnational access to the living lab. Subsequently, the applications are forwarded to the Transnational Access Manager for scrutiny and managing the evaluation procedure.

Figure 22. Backend of the Application Form - Overview

Figure 23. Backend of the Application Form – Entries

4 Conclusions

This deliverable has provided a detailed overview of all the contents and elements that compose the Application Toolkit. The Application Toolkit has effectively supported 116 external researchers who submitted a project proposal in the frame of the 3 Open Calls for Transnational Access. The results of the Open Calls will be described in the upcoming *D11.3 Evaluation Procedure and Accepted Proposals*.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

5 Appendices

5.1 Appendix I

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Offerings per Use Case

In this table you may seek for use cases according to your field of expertise and see which Living Lab Research Infrastructures can support these use cases.

Research Use Case			Living Lab Research Infrastructures																
No.	Researchers' expertise	Brief use case description	LiCalab Older Adults Homes	MOBILAB & Care – Motion Lab	Thomas More Experience Lab	AUTH Living Environment	AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living	AUTH Centrifuge & Rehabilitation Living	AIT Technology Experience Lab	Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab	GAIA and Smart Spaces	GAIA Ocean Living Lab	INTRAS Rehabilitation Living	INTRAS VR/AR Environment and	INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA &	McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab	LifeSpace by UPM	Laurea Simulated Hospital	Laurea Activity Living Lab
1	Accessibility design experts	Validating accessible architectonics and escape route models with VR experiment and real-life simulations.				X	X		X				X	X	X	X			X
2	Applied economics experts	Evaluating cost and performance in different healthcare processes, situations and public health.						X			X	X							

D11.2 Application Toolkit

3	Biomedical researchers	Studying biochemical and physiological functions, investigating how the human body works with the aim of finding new ways to improve health. Biomedical engineering knowledge (Home hospitalization, Transitional Care, Multifunctional interaction), as well as digital biomarkers analysis (e.g., for cognitive state).				x	x	x					x	x	x	x	x		x	
4	Business developers	Studying the product-market fit, matching a solution with a societal need, learning about the user acceptance of products and services, as well as about potential products to develop, willingness to pay, business model and ideal route to market.	x									x	x	x	x	x			x	x
5	Citizen scientists, users as co-researchers	User empowerment, training, design, analysis and implementation of strategies and methodologies for user engagement and for raising awareness and generating citizen participation.	x			x	x		x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
6	Clinical expertise researchers	(Doctors, nurses, healthcare workers, specialists, physiotherapists etc.), conducting research of healthcare services and practices, research on symptomatology or epidemiology of a disease, analysis of clinical effects of research performed in the study, e.g., via real life testing.		x	x	x	x	x					x	x	x	x				x
7	Communication studies experts	Defining written, oral, visual and digital communication within a certain workplace. Evaluating (multi professional) healthcare team collaboration, communication and debriefing in various healthcare situations in simulated environments (especially in Simulation lab).				x			x	x						x			x	x

D11.2 Application Toolkit

8	Computer, technology scientists	Developing systems/tools/ technologies, testing and evaluating an ICT tool, prototype and real-life testing, computer vision & AI, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality, Cybersecurity.	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				x	x	x	x	x		x
9	Data scientists	Collecting, analysing and interpreting digital data, such as data analytics in healthcare and digital patient recordings (how patient information recording process is managed and utilized during the intervention by using digital tools in simulated situations).	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				x	x	x	x			
10	Ergonomics and safety experts	Implementation and validation of ergonomic technologies/services to support workers and system performance, promoting ergonomics in working environments, improving both health/well-being and productivity, while avoiding occupational hazards.					x	x	x				x	x	x			x	x
11	Innovation and design management researchers	Ecosystem and innovation management research, social network analysis. Evaluating how health and wellbeing ecosystem operates between different actors at local, regional, national and international level, including also scaling and commercialization.							x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
12	Neuroscientists	Focusing on the brain and its impact on behaviour and cognitive functions (cognitive neuroscience, EEG-based BMI research, protocol / paradigm testing, study framework evaluation).				x	x	x					x	x	x	x			

D11.2 Application Toolkit

19	Social workers/researchers	Conducting an investigation in accordance with the scientific methods and tools, studying the impact of new care models and/or care innovations on society, developing models for a caring and inclusive society.	X			x				x				x	x	x			x	x	
20	Sport science	Experimenting novel training methods, and their effectiveness in various dimensions such as safety, engagement, and physical capabilities. Studying the impact of physical movements in various functions and wellbeing features.				x		x		x	x	x						x			x
21	UX research and assessment experts	Developing the process for user experience design (UXD, UED, or XD) supporting user behaviour through usability, usefulness, and desirability provided in the interaction with a product or service, addressing all aspects as perceived by users with a focus on the quality of the user experience. Studying and experimenting the best practices for UI/UX and evaluating user's experience in different situations and while using different tools.	x			x	x	x	x					x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x